

Preparation and Study of some Hydroxide Jellies.

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In a previous communication (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, **168**, 214) it was reported that hydroxide jellies of iron, chromium and aluminium can be obtained by treating their metallic chlorides or nitrates with sodium acetate in presence of a small amount of ammonium sulphate and ammonia. In this paper, we have investigated in detail the conditions of formation of the following jellies:—Ferric hydroxide, chromium hydroxide, aluminium hydroxide, stannic hydroxide and zirconium hydroxide.

Ferric Hydroxide Jellies.

For the preparation of this jelly, we started with *M/2*-ferric chloride solution in test tubes and added varying amounts of sodium acetate solution to it. To the red solution thus obtained was added a little of ammonium sulphate solution. A small quantity of ammonia was also added and the mixture, which was acidic, was shaken and allowed to stand for some time. It soon develops opalescence and finally, a gelatinous precipitate or a jelly is obtained according to the concentrations of the various reacting constituents. Thus the jelly is obtained in an acid medium.

The influence of the variation of the concentrations of sodium acetate, ammonium sulphate, ammonia and ferric chloride has been studied in the following tables:

Ferric chloride solution	<i>M/2</i> .
Sodium acetate solution	3 <i>F4N</i> .
Ammonium sulphate	3 <i>M</i> .
Ammonia	5-8 <i>1N</i> .

TABLE I.

Variation of Sodium Acetate.

To 2 c. c. of ferric chloride solution were added 0.5 c. c. of ammonium sulphate and 0.1 c. c. of ammonia and varying concentrations of sodium acetate. The total volume was made up to 5 c. c. in each case by adding the requisite amount of water.

Sodium acetate.	Observation.
0.8 c. c.	Clear solution, no jelly.
0.9	" "
1.0	Turbid solution, no jelly.
1.1	Turbid viscous solution.
1.2	Set to loose jelly in 20 hrs.
1.3	Set to firm opaque jelly in 20 hrs.
1.4	" " "
1.5	Opaque solution, but no jelly.

TABLE II.

Variation of Ammonium Sulphate.

Ferric chloride solution = 2 c. c. Sodium acetate = 1.2 c. c.
 Ammonia = 0.1 c. c. Total volume = 5 c. c.

Ammonium sulphate.	Observation.
0.2 c. c.	Set to loose opaque jelly within 22 hrs.
0.4	" firm " " "
0.6	" " " " 15 "
0.8	" " " " 10 "
1.0	" loose jelly within 22 hrs.

TABLE III.

Variation of Ammonia.

Ferric chloride solution = 2 c. c. Sodium acetate = 1.2 c. c.
 Ammonium sulphate = 0.6 c. c. Total volume = 5 c. c.

Ammonia.	Observation.
0 c. c.	Clear solution, no jelly.
0.1	Set to opaque firm jelly in 22 hrs.
0.2	" " within 22 hrs.
0.3	" loose jelly " "

TABLE IV.

Variation of Ferric Chloride.

Total volume = 5 c. c.

Ferric chloride :.	Sodium acetate.	Ammonium sulphate.	Ammonia.	Observation.
1 c. c.	1.0 c. c.	0.2 c. c.	0.1 c. c.	No jelly, precipitate.
1	1.2	0.5	"	"
1.83	1.0	0.2	"	Opaque loose jelly in 22 hrs.
"	0.8	"	"	" firm " "
"	1.0	"	0	" " " "
2.0	1.2	"	0.1	" " " "

From the results recorded in these tables, it will be seen that for a given amount of ferric chloride, there is a corresponding minimum amount of sodium acetate which must be added before a jelly is expected. A small quantity above this minimum is always favourable, but the addition of larger amounts of sodium acetate will not form the jelly. As regards the addition of ammonium sulphate, a small quantity is always sufficient; the addition of it beyond a limit gives loose jellies or gelatinous precipitates. The addition of a trace of ammonia is sufficient to give a jelly if the concentrations of other constituents are suitable. In some jellies with higher concentrations of ferric chloride, it has been observed that the addition of ammonia is not essential, but if a trace of it is added, the jelly is more easily formed. The jellies of ferric hydroxide obtained by this method are opaque and stable, and do not undergo any marked syneresis and some of them can be preserved for months.

Chromium Hydroxide Jellies.

Our method of preparation of this jelly consists in taking a known amount of chromic chloride solution in test tubes and then adding a sufficient amount of sodium acetate to it. The mixture is allowed to stand for an hour and then some amount of ammonia and then a little of ammonium sulphate are added to it. If the mixture is not allowed to stand for sufficient time before the addition of ammonia, precipitation occurs and no jelly is obtained. The clear

mixture obtained in the way described develops opalescence and finally translucent or opaque violet jellies of fine texture are obtained.

Chromic chloride solution	M/2.
Sodium acetate	3·54N.
Ammonium sulphate	2M.
Ammonia	5·81N.

TABLE V.

Variation of Sodium Acetate.

Chromic chloride solution = 2 c. c. Ammonium sulphate = 0·5 c. c.

Total volume = 5 c. c.

Sodium acetate.	Ammonia.	Observation.
0·7 c. c.	0·7 c. c.	No jelly, slight precipitate.
1·0	"	Translucent violet jelly in 2 hrs. 45 mins.
1·3	"	" " 1½ hrs.
1·5	"	Clear solution, no jelly.
"	1·0	Firm opaque jelly in 2 hrs.
"	0·5	No jelly, clear solution.

TABLE VI.

Variation of Ammonium Sulphate.

Chromic chloride solution = 2 c. c. Sodium acetate = 1·3 c. c.

Ammonia = 0·7 c. c.

Total volume = 5 c. c.

Ammonium sulphate.	Observation.
0·2 c. c.	Firm translucent jelly in 1 hr.
0·5	" " 1½ hrs.
0·7	Firm opaque jelly in 2 hrs.
1·0	" " 2 hrs. 45 mins.

TABLE VII.

Variation of Ammonia.

Chromic chloride solution = 2 c. c. Total volume = 5 c. c.

Sodium acetate.	Ammonium sulphate.	Ammonia.	Observation.
1.5 c. c.	0.5 c. c.	0.5 c. c.	No jelly, clear solution.
"	"	0.7	" " "
"	"	1.0	Firm jelly in 2 hrs.
1.0	"	0.5	No jelly, clear solution.
"	"	0.7	Translucent jelly in 2 hrs. 45 mins.
"	"	1.0	" " 15 hrs.
"	"	1.3	Opaque jelly in 2½ hrs.
"	1.0	1.0	" " 15 hrs.

TABLE VIII.

Variation of Chromic Chloride.

Ammonium sulphate = 0.5 c.c. Total volume = 5 c. c.

Chromic chloride.	Sodium acetate.	Ammonia.	Observation.
2 c. c.	1 c. c.	0.7 c. c.	Translucent jelly in 2 hrs. 45 mins.
1	1	"	Opaque jelly in 22 hrs.
0.5	1	"	Loose jelly in 1 day.
2	1	0.5	No jelly, clear solution.
1	1	"	Translucent jelly in 4½ hrs.
0.5	1	"	Loose jelly in 1 day.
"	1.5	1.0	Opalescent solution, no jelly.

Just as in the case of ferric hydroxide jellies, in this case also, a minimum amount of sodium acetate is fixed for a given amount of chromic chloride for jelly formation. Similarly, the addition of greater quantities of ammonium sulphate always gives jellies of weaker texture in a longer time. The regulation of the quantity of ammonia is an important factor in the formation of this

jelly, and a sufficient amount of ammonia has always to be added before a jelly could be expected. The addition of ammonia above a fixed minimum always diminishes the time of setting. The jellies obtained with dilute solutions of chromic chloride are translucent and those with concentrated solutions are opaque. The jellies are stable and of fine texture and do not undergo any marked syneresis.

Aluminium Hydroxide Jellies.

In our method of preparation of this jelly, a known amount of aluminium nitrate solution is taken in test tubes and varying concentrations of sodium acetate and ammonium sulphate are added to it. To the mixture is then added the requisite amount of ammonia, drop by drop with constant stirring; and thus a clear colourless solution is obtained which soon develops opalescence on standing, and if the concentrations are favourable, firm translucent or opaque jellies are obtained. These jellies are stable and quite uniform in texture. The influence of the variation of concentrations of different constituents is recorded in the following tables:—

Aluminium nitrate	M/2.
Sodium acetate	3.54 N.
Ammonium sulphate	2M.
Ammonia	5.81 N.

TABLE IX.

Variation of Sodium Acetate.

Aluminium nitrate solution = 2 c.c. Ammonia = 0.5 c.c.
Total volume = 5 c.c.

Sodium acetate.	Ammonium sulphate.	Observation.
1 c.c.	0.5 c.c.	Transparent jelly in 3 days.
1	0.7	Translucent jelly within 22 hrs.
1.2	0.7	Precipitate, no jelly.
1.5	0.7	Precipitate, no jelly.
1.8	0.7	Precipitate, no jelly.

TABLE X.

Variation of Ammonium Sulphate.

Aluminium nitrate solution = 2 c.c. Sodium acetate = 1 c.c.
 Ammonia = 0.5 c.c. Total volume = 5 c.c.

Ammonium sulphate.	Observation.
0.5 c.c.	Transparent jelly in 3 days.
0.7	Translucent jelly in 22 hrs.
1.0	" " "
1.3	Opaque jelly within 22 hrs.
1.6	" " "

TABLE XI.

Variation of Ammonia.

Aluminium nitrate solution = 2 c.c. Sodium acetate = 1 c.c.
 Total volume = 5 c.c.

Ammonium sulphate.	Ammonia.	Observation.
0.5 c.c.	0.5 c.c.	Transparent jelly in 3 days.
0.6	0.6	Translucent jelly in 27 hrs.
0.7	0.7	White precipitate, no jelly.
0.8	0.8	" " "
0.9	0.9	Transparent jelly in 3 days.
1.0	1.0	Translucent jelly in 26 hrs.
1.1	1.1	Translucent jelly within 22 hrs.
1.2	1.2	" " "

TABLE XII.

Variation of Aluminium Nitrate.

Total volume = 5 c.c.

Aluminium nitrate.	Sodium acetate.	Ammonium sulphate.	Ammonia	Observation.
2 c.c. of 0.5M	1.0 c.c.	0.7 c.c.	0.8 c.c.	Translucent jelly in 22 hrs.
2 of 0.75M	1.1	0.7	0.5	Translucent jelly in 2 days.
2 "	1.1	0.8	0.5	" " "
2 "	1.1	0.9	0.5	" " "
2 "	1.1	0.7	0.6	Precipitate, no jelly.
1 of 0.5M	1.0	0.7	0.5	No jelly.

Firm transparent or translucent jellies are obtained by this method. In some cases, the opalescence increases with time and finally, the jellies become opaque. There appears to be a very limited range over which the quantity of sodium acetate could be varied. The addition of large amounts of ammonium sulphate slightly decreases the time of setting, but increases the opacity of the jelly.

The greater the concentration of ammonium sulphate, the less will be the amount of ammonia to give a jelly. The regulation of the quantity of ammonia is also an important factor, for which a minimum concentration is necessary, but the addition of it in amounts greater than the minimum gives either opaque loose jellies or precipitates.

Stannic Hydroxide Jellies.

Weiser (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1922, 26, 654) claims to have obtained transparent jellies of stannic hydroxide by coagulating a sol of stannic oxide prepared by Zeigmondy's method. Our method for the preparation of iron, chromium, and aluminium jellies can be extended to obtain stannic hydroxide jellies. The jellies obtained by this method are mostly opaque, but some are translucent at the time of formation but become opaque on standing. Some of the jellies have a tendency to synerise. *M/2*-Solution of tin tetrachloride (liquid, Kahlbaum) was taken in test tubes, and to it varying concentrations of sodium acetate and a little of ammonium sulphate were added. The solution soon develops opalescence and finally a jelly is obtained. The addition of ammonia is not necessary to obtain this jelly, but in certain cases, specially when the solution is obtained by dissolving hydrated crystals of stannic chloride which always contain free hydrochloric acid, the addition of ammonia is essential to obtain a jelly.

Stannic chloride	<i>M/2</i> .
Sodium acetate	3.54 <i>N</i> .
Ammonium sulphate	2 <i>M</i> .
Ammonia	5.81 <i>N</i> .

TABLE XIII.

Variation of Sodium Acetate.

Stannic chloride solution = 2 c.c. Ammonium sulphate = 0.5 c.c.

No ammonia was added. Total volume = 5 c.c.

Sodium acetate.	Observation.
0.5 c.c.	Clear solution, no jelly.
0.7	Clear solution, no jelly.
0.9	Opaque jelly in 1 day.
1.0	Opaque jelly in 1 day, slight syneresis after 2 days.
1.2	Immediately opaque jelly, readily undergoing syneresis.

TABLE XIV.

Variation of Ammonium Sulphate.

Stannic chloride solution = 2 c.c. Sodium acetate = 1 c.c.
 No ammonia was added Total volume = 5 c.c.

Ammonium sulphate.	Observation.
0.5 c. c.	Opaque jelly in 1 day.
0.6	Opaque jelly in 14 minutes, syneresis starting after 5 hrs.
0.7	Opaque jelly in 10 minutes, syneresis soon starts.
0.9	Opaque jelly in 2 minutes, syneresis soon starts and the jelly breaks up in a day.

TABLE XV.

Variation of Ammonia.

Stannic chloride solution = 2 c.c. Sodium acetate = 0.7 c.c.
 Ammonium sulphate = 0.5 c.c. Total volume = 5 c.c.

Ammonia.	Observation.
0 c. c.	Clear solution, no jelly.
0.1	White opaque jelly in 32 hrs.
0.2	White opaque jelly in 23 hrs.
0.3	Loose jelly immediately, which soon breaks up.
0.4	" " " "

TABLE XVI.

Variation of Stannic Chloride.

No ammonia was added. Total volume = 5 c. c.

Stannic chloride.	Sodium acetate.	Ammonium sulphate.	Observation.
1 c. c.	0.5 c. c.	0.5 c. c.	Precipitate, but no jelly.
1	0.5	0.1	Opaque jelly in 10 min., undergoing syneresis in 1 day.
2	0.5	0.1	No jelly.
1	0.4	0.1	Firm opaque jelly in 1 day, slight syneresis after 2 days.
2	0.4	0.1	No jelly.

It will be seen from these tables that there is a limited range of sodium acetate which will produce a jelly. The jellies obtained by the addition of large amounts of either sodium acetate or ammonium sulphate begin to synerise at once. The addition of ammonia appears to be favourable where the concentrations of sodium acetate and ammonium sulphate are insufficient to give jellies.

Zirconium Hydroxide Jellies.

We have observed that opaque white jellies of zirconium hydroxide are obtained by simply adding the solution of sodium acetate to zirconium nitrate solution, and allowing the mixture to stand for some time. The addition of potassium or ammonium sulphate is not essential though favourable for the jelly formation. Like stannic hydroxide jellies, the addition of ammonia is not required. The jellies obtained by this method are opaque or translucent at the time of setting, but become opaque on standing. Some of the jellies are stable while others melt, break or synerise after a time.

TABLE XVII.

Total volume = 5 c. c.

Zirconium-nitrate (M/2).	Sodium-acetate (3'54-N).	Observation.
1 c. c.	0'2 c. c.	Clear solution, no jelly.
1	0'3	Clear solution, no jelly.
1	0'5	Translucent jelly in 2½ min., not synerising in 1 day.
1	0'7	Translucent jelly in 1½ min., not synerising in 1 day.
2	0'8	Clear solution, no jelly.
2	0'4	" " "
2	0'45	" " "
2	0'5	Translucent jelly in 4 min., synerising in a day.
2	0'6	Translucent jelly in 1½ min., which soon becomes opaque, and synerises in a day.
2	0'7	Opaque jelly in ¼ min., synerising after 6 hrs.
2	0'8	" " "
2	1'0	Opaque loose jelly in 1 min.
2	1'3	" "
2	2'0	" "
2	2'5	" "
3	0'5	No jelly, clear solution.
3	0'7	Translucent jelly in 1 min.
3	1'0	Opaque jelly in 20 sec.
4	0'7	No jelly.
4	1'0	Opaque jelly in 10 sec.

TABLE XVIII.

Influence of Sulphate Ions.

M/2-Zirconium nitrate solution = 2 c. c. Total volume = 5 c. c.

Potassium-sulphate.	Sodium-acetate (3.54 <i>N</i>).	Observation.
0 c. c.	0.4 c. c.	Clear solution, no jelly.
0.1	0.4	Translucent jelly in 5 minutes, no syneresis in 1 day.
0.2	0.4	Opaque jelly in $\frac{1}{2}$ min.
0.3	0.4	Opaque jelly in 5 sec.
0	0.5	Translucent jelly in 4 min.
0.1	0.5	Opaque jelly in 1 min.
0	0.8	No jelly, clear solution.
0.5	0.8	Opaque jelly in $\frac{1}{2}$ min.
0.7	0.8	White precipitate immediately but no jelly.

In this investigation of hydroxide jellies, we have tried to study the gelation properties in a comparative way by keeping the concentrations of the metallic halides or nitrates constant in all the cases. In view of the fact that the formation of jellies appears to be a function of the variable concentrations of no less than four different substances; *e.g.*, metallic salts, sodium acetate, ammonia and ammonium sulphate, and also other numerous products of reaction, the whole system becomes very complex. It has been long known that when chromic chloride solution is boiled with sodium acetate and then made alkaline with caustic alkali, it sets to a jelly. Moreover, ferrio, chromic and aluminium hydroxide sols are prepared by the addition of sodium acetate to their salts and dialysing the mixtures. The probable mechanism of the jelly formation with these hydroxides can easily be explained by assuming the formation of colloidal hydroxides by the interaction of metallic salts with sodium acetate.

The metallic hydroxides are stabilised by the absorption of metallic and hydrogen ions given out in the solution. In some cases the stability is so great, that any amount of the coagulating electrolyte is insufficient to neutralise the charge. However, by the addition of suitable amounts of ammonia, hydrogen ions are decreased and the system becomes more liable to coagulation.

In previous publications, we have shown in the cases of both hydrophobe and hydrophile colloids that under similar conditions, uncharged particles are more hydrated than the charged ones, and as the charge is gradually diminished, the sol becomes more and more viscous. Our results on the changes on viscosity during the process of gelation (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 891) of various inorganic jellies also support the view that as the charge is continuously neutralised, the system becomes more and more viscous. The function of ammonium sulphate in the above jellies is also similar. In the presence of a suitable concentration of hydrogen ions, ammonium sulphate brings about the gradual diminution of the positive charge of the particles, and as the charge diminishes, the system becomes more and more viscous, and finally a jelly is obtained. Our results recorded in the previous tables show that there is always a fixed optimum range of the concentration of ammonium sulphate necessary for jelly formation. Any amount less than that will either give unstable loose jellies or precipitates. We have shown that after the neutralisation of the charge, the uncharged particles either tend to adsorb the solvent medium or to agglomerate with one another. In some cases in the presence of the coagulating electrolytes, both the tendencies of hydration and agglomeration go side by side and finally opaque jellies are obtained. By varying the concentrations of ammonium sulphate, we have shown that at higher concentrations of the electrolyte, the jellies produced are very loose, and in some cases, only precipitates have been obtained. This is due to the fact that the agglomeration tendency of the particles is preponderating over the hydration tendency in these cases.

As the stability of the colloidal metallic hydroxides produced by the action of sodium acetate and metallic salts depends upon the hydrogen ions adsorbed by them, the time of gelation and the nature of the jelly are also affected by the hydrogen ion concentrations of the system. Thus the regulation of hydrogen ions is also a very important factor in the formation of these jellies. The results given in the two following tables show the comparative hydrogen ion concentrations of the metallic salt solutions and also of the same salt solutions when mixed with those amounts of sodium acetate which would give jellies on the addition of the proper amounts of ammonium sulphate and ammonia. Quinhydrone electrode and vernier potentiometer of Cambridge Instrument Co. were used to determine electromotive forces against normal potassium chloride—calomel electrode.

TABLE XIX.

8 C. c. of $M/2$ -salt in 20 c.c.	$E.M.F.$ in volts.	P_H .	c_H .
Ferric chloride	0.412	0.069	8.53×10^{-1}
Chromic chloride	0.254	2.79	1.62×10^{-2}
Aluminium nitrate	0.271	2.60	3.16×10^{-3}
Zirconium nitrate	0.343	1.28	5.49×10^{-3}
Stannic chloride	0.364	0.90	1.26×10^{-1}

TABLE XX.

8 C.c. of $M/2$ -solution of salts were taken. Total volume=20 c.c.

Salts.	Sodium acetate added.	$E.M.F.$ in volts.	P_H .	c_H .
Ferric chloride	3.6 c.c.	0.178	4.10	7.95×10^{-5}
Chromic chloride	5.2	0.181	4.05	8.91×10^{-5}
Aluminium nitrate	4.0	0.208	3.59	2.57×10^{-5}
Zirconium nitrate	2.0	0.162	4.38	4.16×10^{-5}
Stannic chloride	4.0	0.362	0.93	1.17×10^{-1}

These results show that by the addition of sodium acetate to metallic salts, there is a considerable diminution in hydrogen ion concentration and a further diminution is observed when ammonia is added to the solution. The following table shows the hydrogen ion concentrations of the final systems which give rise to jellies.

TABLE XXI.

8 C.c. of $M/2$ -salts taken. Total volume=20 c.c.

Metallic hydroxide.	3.5 <i>N</i> -Sodium acetate.	2 <i>M</i> -Ammonium sulphate.	5.81 <i>N</i> -Ammonia.	$E.M.F.$ in volts.	P_H .	c_H .
Ferric	3.6 c.c.	2 c.c.	0.4 c.c.	0.155	4.50	3.16×10^{-5}
Chromic	5.2	2	2.8	0.095	5.53	2.95×10^{-5}
Aluminium	4.0	2.8	2.0	0.135	4.84	1.44×10^{-5}
Zirconium	2.0	...	...	0.162	4.38	4.16×10^{-5}
Stannic	4.0	2.0	...	0.351	1.12	7.59×10^{-5}

The hydrogen ions of the initial metallic salt solutions of these five jelly-forming substances are in the following order:—

Ferric > stannic > zirconium > aluminium > chromic.

By the addition of sodium acetate, the order of the hydrogen ion concentrations becomes—

Stannic > aluminium > chromic > ferric > zirconium.

Finally, by the addition of all the necessary constituents of jelly formation, the order becomes—

Stannic > zirconium > ferric > aluminium > chromic. It shows that all the jellies cannot be obtained at the same hydrogen ion concentrations. The difference so obtained is to be explained on the basis of the intrinsic nature of the metals themselves. From our results on hydrogen ion concentrations, it appears that the metals which give jellies most readily are those which on the addition of sodium acetate, ammonia, etc., possess the system of the greatest hydrogen ion concentrations such as tin and zirconium. But the jellies which are obtained in a weaker hydrogen ion concentration medium, as iron, aluminium and chromium are the most stable and best in texture undergoing no marked syneresis.

In a previous paper (*loc. cit.*), we have classified the jellies on the basis of their transparency, and have stated that whenever the hydration tendency is the greatest, the jellies will be transparent, and the agglomeration tendency of the particles gives rise to opacity. Of the five hydroxide jellies investigated in this paper, aluminium hydroxide jellies, though opalescent are the most transparent. The zirconium hydroxide jellies are translucent when freshly formed but they become opaque in a few hours. Chromic hydroxide jellies are slightly translucent, though mostly opaque, while stannic and ferric hydroxide jellies are opaque. Thus the opacity of these jellies appears to be in the following order—

Stannic > ferric > chromic > zirconium > aluminium.

From this it appears that the hydration tendency of the particles is more marked in the case of aluminium and zirconium than in the case of chromium, iron, or tin.

The same method for the preparation of hydroxide jellies have been employed in the case of other metals like copper, cobalt, nickel, thorium, mercury and cadmium but the results so far obtained are negative. Weiser's preparation (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1923, 27, 685) of copper hydroxide jellies from copper acetate, ammonia, and

ammonium sulphate also appears to be similar to that of ours. It appears that with hydroxides of copper cobalt, nickel, cadmium and thorium, the tendency of the particles is more towards agglomeration than hydration, and the hydroxide colloids formed are very unstable and their particles do not develop marked hydration even when slowly coagulated.

Summary.

1. The jellies of iron, chromium, and aluminium hydroxides have been obtained by treating the metallic chlorides or nitrates with sodium acetate, ammonium sulphate and ammonia in suitable concentrations, the details of which have been investigated in a comparative way by varying the concentration of different jelly-forming constituents.

2. The jellies of zirconium hydroxide have been obtained by the addition of only sodium acetate to zirconium nitrate solution. The addition of sulphate ions favours the formation of this jelly; addition of ammonia is not necessary.

3. The jellies of stannic hydroxide have been obtained by the addition of sodium acetate and ammonium sulphate to stannic chloride solution. No addition of ammonia is necessary unless there is much free acid in the stannic chloride solution.

4. The mechanism of the formation of these hydroxide jellies has been explained on the assumption of the formation of colloidal hydroxides by the action of sodium acetate to the metallic salts, which are stabilised by the adsorption of metallic and hydrogen ions. The function of ammonia is to reduce the hydrogen ions to such an extent as to make the system liable to coagulation by ammonium sulphate. The ammonium sulphate gradually reduces the positive charge of the colloidal particles, and the system thereby becomes more viscous and hydrated, and finally the jellies are obtained.

5. All these jellies have been obtained in the acid medium. The comparative study of hydrogen ion concentrations of the jelly-forming systems shows that the jellies of different metals cannot be obtained at the same hydrogen ion concentrations. But the jellies most readily obtained are of those metals, as zirconium or tin, which on the addition of jelly-forming constituents give a medium of the greatest hydrogen ion concentrations. But these jellies are less

stable in comparison with those obtained in a medium of less hydrogen ion concentrations, as of the aluminium, chromium and iron.

6. The hydroxide jellies of nickel, cobalt, copper, cadmium, mercury and thorium could not be obtained as yet by the method used for the preparation of iron, chromium and other hydroxide jellies. It appears that in the case of these substances, the agglomeration tendency of the particles is more pronounced than the hydration tendency.

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